

Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution

Grant Agreement Number: 101095253

D.6.1. Early Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and Activities

Document Identification			
Status	Final	Due Date	31/10/2023
Version	1.0	Submission Date	30/10/2023
Related WP	WP6	Document Reference	D.6.1.
Related Deliverable(s)	N/A	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Participant	EURISY	Document Type:	DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
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Document History			
Version	Date	Modified by	Modification reason
0.1	28/09/2023	Anaïs Guy	First draft
0.2	29/03/2023	Annalisa Donati	Internal review
0.3	02/10/2023	Anaïs Guy	Internal review
0.4	05/10/2023	Irini Krimpa & Dimitris Maragkos	Reviewers
0.5	05/10/2023	Deniz Ikiz Kaya	Reviewers
0.6	12/10/2023	Anaïs Guy	Reviewers' comments implementation
0.7	20/10/2023	Annalisa Donati	Internal review
0.8	23/10/2023	Dimitris Maragkos	Reviewers
0.9	25/10/2023	Anaïs Guy	Quality review comments implementation
1.0	26/10/2023	Anaïs Guy	Final version to be submitted

Quality Control		
Role	Who (Partner short name)	Approval Date
Deliverable leader	EURISY	20/10/2023
Quality manager	ICCS	25/10/2023
Project Coordinator	ICCS	26/10/2023

Abstract

The THETIDA project approaches safeguarding and protecting Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage from the effects of climate change and natural hazards in a holistic manner that includes risk management, protection and preparedness, as complementary strategies to prevent damages to CH sites, identify and ward off additional threats and promote policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas. THETIDA project achieves this goal through the development of a preventive conservation strategy that includes monitoring, risk preparedness and management, for underwater and coastal CH (U&C-CH) sites, identify and ward off additional threats and promote adaptation, reconstruction and other post-disruption strategies to restore normal conditions to the historic area, as well as long-term strategic approaches to adapt to CC and to wield policy tools for economic resilience. In this project, an interdisciplinary team of researchers, experts and practitioners will develop, test and validate an integrated multiple heritage risk assessment and protection system with evidence-based monitoring frameworks, innovative tools and instruments and through participatory processes (Citizens' Science and Living Labs). The project implementation actions will link the social innovations with cutting-edge technologies (ICT and IoT harmonised tools).

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Disclaimer of warranties

This document is part of the deliverables from the project THETIDA, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101095253.

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable 6.1. provides a detailed overview of the Early Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan and Activities for the THETIDA project. Firstly, the deliverable details the roadmap to be followed by all partners to ensure effective and insightful communication and dissemination measures, as well as the variety of audiences targeted by these measures in the framework of the THETIDA project. Communication and dissemination (C&D) actions identified to successfully achieve the objectives set out in this plan are presented. The online and offline tools and channels used throughout the duration of the project are detailed in accordance with the assets they bring to THETIDA project. The deliverable also addresses internal communication rules to be followed by THETIDA partners during the project's lifetime, and a Sustainability plan to ensure the viability of the project after the funding period, in line with the Horizon Europe guidelines. Before the conclusion, the deliverable also provides a summary of the key performance indicators (KPIs) that partners will aim at attaining during the project to certify the optimal outcome of the C&D plan.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction to THETIDA Project	10
2. Communication and Dissemination Plan	11
2.1. Structure of the Communication and Dissemination Plan	11
2.2. Roadmap and Timeline	13
2.3. Objectives of the Communication and Dissemination Plan	15
3. THETIDA Audience	20
4. Tools and Channels	23
4.1. Communication Strategy	23
4.1.1. Visual Identity	23
4.1.2. Online Tools	25
4.1.3. Offline Tools and Channels	30
4.2. Dissemination of Scientific and Technical Results	33
4.2.1. Open Science Practices applied in the Project	35
4.2.2. Tools and Channels Summary	36
5. Internal Communication	38
6. Sustainability Plan	39
6.1. Exploitation Strategies	39
6.2. Project’s Sustainability Tools	40
6.2.1. Online Presence	40
6.2.2. Sustainability Communication Guidelines	41
6.2.3. Participatory Processes and Citizen’s Involvement	41
6.2.4. Scientific, Technical and Industrial Engagement with Project’s Results	42
7. Monitoring Communication and Dissemination Plan’s success (KPIs)	43
8. Conclusion	46
References	47
Annex 1: Communication Guidelines	48
Annex 2: THETIDA Website Pages	54
Annex 3: THETIDA Social Media Channels	58

List of Figures

Figure 1: Roadmap	13
Figure 2: C&D Plan Timeline	15
Figure 3: Timeline and KPIs	19
Figure 4: THETIDA Colours and Fonts	25
Figure 5: e-Newsletter Website Subscription	29

List of Tables

Table 1: C&D Updates	12
Table 2: Steps and Objectives Summary	16
Table 3: Target Audiences	21
Table 4: Website KPIs	26
Table 5: Social Media KPIs	28
Table 6: e-Newsletter and e-mail Campaigns KPIs	29
Table 7: General Spreading KPIs	30
Table 8: Promotional Material KPIs	31
Table 9: Potential Events	32
Table 10: Events KPIS	33
Table 11: Identified Scientific Publications	34
Table 12: Dissemination KPIs	35
Table 13: Tools and Channels Summary	36
Table 14: KPIs Summary	44

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
C&D	Communication and dissemination
D6.1	Deliverable number 1 belonging to WP 6
EC	European Commission
KPIs	Key Impact Indicators
LLs	Living Labs
PC	Project Coordinator
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction to THETIDA Project

The THETIDA project approaches safeguarding and protecting Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage from the effects of climate change and natural hazards in a holistic manner including risk management, protection and preparedness, as complementary strategies to prevent damages to cultural heritage sites, identify and ward off additional threats and promote policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas.

THETIDA aims at achieving this goal through three main axis: **(i)** the development of a preventive conservation strategy that includes monitoring, risk preparedness and management, for underwater and coastal cultural heritage (underwater and coastal) sites, identify and ward off additional threats; **(ii)** the promotion of adaptation, reconstruction and other post-disruption strategies to restore normal conditions to the historic area; **(iii)** the development of long-term strategic approaches to adapt to climate change and to wield policy tools for economic resilience.

In this project, an interdisciplinary team of researchers, experts and practitioners will develop, test, and validate an integrated multiple heritage risk assessment and protection system with evidence-based monitoring frameworks, innovative tools and instruments, and through participatory processes (Citizens' Science and Living Labs). The project implementation actions will link social innovations with cutting-edge technologies (Information Communication and Technologies -ICT- Tools and Internet of Things -IoT- harmonised tools).

While THETIDA aims at developing multiple hazard assessment tools and strengthening maritime cultural heritage management practices, it also aims at promoting the use of specific technologies (*e.g.*, Copernicus data) beyond the space and/or scientific community.

In relation to THETIDA objectives, the expected outcomes of the project include **building inclusive multi-stakeholder communities** for establishing sustainable participatory processes for co-designing and co-creating risk assessment and adaptation strategies taking sociocultural values at their core and **bridge the common communication and knowledge gaps between scientific and local actors.**

As communication and dissemination activities are crucial for the success of the objectives of the project, and to ensure the project's compliance with Horizon Europe Guidelines, this deliverable is going to detail the communication and dissemination plan established by C&D Work Package (WP) leader Eurisy to safeguard THETIDA C&D activities success. The C&D plan will successively address the essential points constituting a C&D plan: its objectives, timeline, and the strategy it conveys; the audience targeted by C&D activities and the tools and channels used to address the audience; the methods developed to prevent miscommunication within the consortium; the strategies identified to ensure the

sustainability of the C&D plan. Finally, the present document will provide a summary of KPIs and a conclusion of the leading arguments developed in deliverable 6.1.

2. Communication and Dissemination Plan

2.1. Structure of the Communication and Dissemination Plan

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and Activities is a project deliverable under Work Package 6 ‘Dissemination, communication and exploitation’, drafted in the first six months of the project, and to be continuously updated.

As mentioned within the Grant Agreement, the project C&D methodology is largely based on the Awareness, Interest, Desire and Action (AIDA) model. [1] This approach highlights the necessary steps to gain insights on users’ behavioural patterns and guarantee successful communication activities. These stages are considered to be intertwined into a consecutive chain including:

- **Attention:** this first stage aims at enticing the target audience to pay attention to the project, through a powerful initial impact. The primary objective is to contact as many potential audiences as possible and to capture their attention by introducing the project’s objectives and methodologies. To achieve that, promotional material and social media campaigns are usually developed.
- **Interest:** once the audience’s attention and interest has been captured, it must be maintained in order to keep the audience engaged. At this point, C&D activities have to present compelling information that resonates with the audience, its expertise, occupations, and core activities. This answers the audience needs to obtain additional information about the project.
- **Desire (or Decision):** the purpose of this stage is to foster a sense of desire or want in the minds of the audience, or to foster a decision of the audience to engage with the project. The core idea is to create a connection between the project and the audience’s aspirations and goals. Testimonials and success stories are often used at that stage to emphasise how the offering can fulfil the audience’s needs and desire. This step can occur concurrently with the second one or come after.
- **Action:** this final stage aims at getting the audience to initiate action. In the framework of THETIDA, action can mean using one of the methodologies developed within the project or exploiting the data collected, or the results and outcomes of the project, for instance.

The four communication stages described by the AIDA approach will be complemented by a multi-actor, multi-step, and multi-channels approach detailed in the present document to secure the success of the C&D plan. The C&D plan is therefore based on two complementary approaches, as the first describes a traditional course of action to be followed to ensure the

success of the C&D plan, while the second details how the course of action will be followed. Consequently, the AIDA model will be implemented through the multi- approach. The multi-actor facet of the method reflects the wide spectrum of audiences targeted within the framework of THETIDA (see Chapter 2), as well as the diversity of partners involved in the project and their complementary types of knowledge (e.g. scientific, technical, practical, etc.). Moreover, THETIDA’s C&D plan encompasses different steps described in Section 1.2 and identified to clarify C&D actions. Finally, the C&D plan will follow the multi-channel approach as C&D activities will use a variety of online and offline tools and channels including, social media platforms, attendance to and organisation of events (in-person and online), publications in scientific and technical journals, etc.

The present document includes a communication and dissemination plan, detailing external and internal C&D actions, as well as a Sustainability plan. Both documents have been prepared by Eurisy and are addressed to THETIDA consortium, as well as external stakeholders and the European Commission.

All partners are called to support communication and dissemination activities, and to provide inputs on their own activities to help maximising the impact of THETIDA, in a timely manner and as defined within the [Communication and Dissemination Guidelines](#) (see Annex 1) distributed to the partners.

The present document will be updated throughout the project lifetime to ensure that the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy is in line with the project’s developments and the long-term sustainability of its results.

Table 1 below shows the preliminary dates identified for the delivery of major updates to this plan. The dates identified below may change along the project duration.

Table 1: C&D Updates

Project Timeline	Title	Deliverable Date
M03 – M06	Early Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and Activities	M06
M06 – M18	Midterm Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and Activities	M18
M18 – M36	Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and Activities	M36

This C&D plan is structured as follows: Chapter 1 details the main steps to be undertaken to successfully achieve the objectives of the C&D plan. Chapter 2 will identify the main targeted audiences of the project and set the strategies to address and engage them from the very early stages of development of the THETIDA project onwards. Therefore, Chapter 3 will be dedicated to presenting the different tools and channels that have been selected and that will be operated to achieve the C&D objectives. Chapter 4 will discuss the internal communication measures and strategies that have been prepared in order to guarantee effective communication among partners. Chapter 5 will complement the above by providing the Sustainability plan describing actions to ensure project visibility, after the natural project lifetime. Finally, Chapter 6 will give a thorough overview of the different indicators that will be used to monitor the success of the C&D actions described in the present plan.

For the purpose of this plan, and to provide a common understanding, the following definition of communication and dissemination has been used in accordance with the Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2021-2024.

Communication and dissemination activities are closely intertwined, by their common objective to divulge information, but they target different publics and therefore diverge in actions and tools. While communication activities target the general public (citizens, experts, potential partners, etc.), dissemination efforts are focused on a specific public made of scientific experts from various fields able to use the results from the project for their own work. Exploitation on the other hand concerns the concrete uses of results produced within the project. These concrete uses can be commercial, societal and/or political depending on the results themselves. [2]

2.2. Roadmap and Timeline

The C&D activities regarding the THETIDA project will follow four main steps, based on the project's expected developments and outcomes, but pertaining only to C&D activities:

Figure 1: Roadmap

In the beginning of the project, in what can be considered as **Step 0**, fundamental actions to initiate C&D activities have been taken: setting-up communication tools such as the definition of visual identity, the developing the website, establishing social media channels. A desk research to map the stakeholders will be carried out in this preliminary phase of the project. The stakeholder map will be developed in cooperation with all the consortium members, it will cluster the stakeholders into groups numbered in a crescent order from the most relevant to the least one. This step was completed by M03.

Step 1: At this stage, the principal effort for consortium partners is to promote the project among stakeholders, experts and practitioners (target group n°1), and their own networks. This first step is meant to last about six months following the kick-off meeting of the project. The main objective is to build a strong basis of interest around the project objectives, methodology and results with communities working directly in the reference fields.

Step 2: From M06 onwards, the goal to be pursued by the C&D partners, with the support of consortium partners, will be to grow and enlarge the community of interest. At this stage, in parallel to the targeted group of interested stakeholders and end-users (target group n°1), the communication will aim at reaching communities not yet involved, as well as the general public (target group n°2). Through the use of social media campaigns, newsletters and videos, the C&D WP will provide engaging material relevant for the different media and communities to increase awareness, engagement and participation. Moreover, project partners will also gather input, design and implement a set of participatory initiatives such as Living Labs, citizen science apps and crowdsourcing initiatives aiming at engaging local and national communities to take action. THETIDA partners will also participate in external events to promote the project's objectives and methodology towards diverse communities previously mentioned.

Step 3: As soon as the first results and outcomes of the project are available and ready for non-confidential disclosure, dissemination activities will start, based on the preliminary clustering process to identify scientific and technical communities. At this stage, participatory processes described above (*i.e.* local workshops, Living Labs) will be running in all pilots sites' countries and beyond. Content and material related to C&D activities will be complemented by result-oriented information while keeping an outreach-oriented approach to ensure a widespread awareness of project's outcomes and results, including among audiences having an incidental interest in the project (target group n°3). Therefore, there will be parallel movements of community growth, by means of outreach actions, and specific targeting through scientific and technical dissemination actions.

Step 4: To ensure the project's sustainability, it is crucial to secure communities' dynamics by maintaining C&D efforts after the funding period of the project. To support a concrete exploitation of the products developed through THETIDA beyond the project partners and early users, C&D material will be further complemented by dedicated information and new narratives on the integration and use of such solutions as well as the related benefits. At this stage additional interactive material will also be produced including stakeholders' interviews and feedback.

The C&D Plan is foreseen to observe the following timeline. It should be noted that this timeline is indicative and might be re-assessed at a later stage to fit THETIDA developments, especially for step 3 which regards results exploitation. Step 1 will start in the early beginnings of the project and will be the main line of action until M06, when it will be complemented by step 2. As step 2 is the logical continuity of Step 1 and is characterised by an intensification of C&D activities, it will start on M06 and will carry on for at least three years after the end of

the funding period of the project (M36). Step 3 will start from M18 and continue for three years after the end of the funding period of the project. Finally, step 4 will start from M30 and will persist for three years after the end of the funding period.

In parallel with the evolution of the different steps of the C&D plan, Eurisy will monitor C&D activities progresses monthly to ascertain that targets are reached. Eurisy will report these progresses to the project coordinator (ICCS) to exchange on corrective measures to distribute among WP6 partners and the whole consortium. An Excel Sheet has been developed to keep a record of these progresses and will be updated monthly by Eurisy.

Figure 2: C&D Plan Timeline

2.3. Objectives of the Communication and Dissemination Plan

The C&D Plan aims to define all communication, dissemination and exploitation actions and activities planned in the framework of the project to:

- i) increase the visibility of the project and its outcomes;
- ii) provide the project with effective tools to ensure awareness;
- iii) ensure the proper diffusion and uptake of project results in accordance with the Horizon Europe C&D policy.

Besides general objectives carried by the C&D plan, there are also specific objectives pertaining to each aforementioned step. To guarantee that these objectives are successfully achieved, landmarks and KPIs have been identified for each step.

Establishing an efficient C&D plan could ensure the success of THETIDA project as a whole on different levels. First, raising awareness on the project is a crucial element to create communities of stakeholders and to reach out to potential end-users. As the project relies partly on participatory processes such as Living Labs (LLs) and Citizen Science and aims to bridge the gap between experts and citizens, an effective C&D plan should provide

opportunities for these communities to learn about and engage with the project. Thus, targeting appropriate audiences is a deciding factor for the success of the C&D plan. Moreover, the technologies developed within the project such as remote sensing of environmental and pollution stressors through satellite, aerial, and ground monitoring, high resolution monitoring technologies, as well as the scientific developments of deterioration models, predication platforms, and ocean model data products (e.g., forecasting Systems and Climatological Hazard Maps) will also require adequate dissemination and exploitation strategies to optimize their beneficial uses.

The following table introduces the objectives of the project and links them to coherent landmarks identified to clarify C&D activities that will take place in each step of the C&D plan. To monitor the success of C&D activities, KPIs have been identified based on the Target Value Objectives defined within the Grant Agreement. These KPIs will be assessed by M18 and by M36 to allow a mid-term evaluation of the project and a report in D.6.2 and a final evaluation and reporting within D.6.3. The final assessment of KPIs will take place at the end of step 3 and in the early beginnings of step 4 to ensure that the dissemination and exploitation activities have had time to be completed and to ensure that the sustainability plan is relevant to this assessment.

Table 2: Steps and Objectives Summary

Steps	Objectives	Landmarks	KPIs
Step 0: Establish C&D tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of project's communication tools Development of project's visibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Definition of a visual identity (logo, colours, etc.) Launch of a website by M03 Creation of social media accounts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design >3 different logos by M03
Step 1: Raise Project Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop project visibility among THETIDA partners, potential end-users and stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share social media platforms among THETIDA partners and their networks Establish a first basis of interest around the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No KPIs have been identified here as this step is considered to be an initial step aiming to lay the foundations of efficient C&D activities
Step 2: Growth and Targeting of Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of a community around the project including the general public and targeted audiences (cf. 2. Audience) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of first social media campaigns (from M06 onwards) Start of quarterly newsletters (from M06 onwards) Organisation and participation to events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have a total of > 2,000 followers on all social media platforms by M18 Have distributed a total of 4 newsletters by M18 Have a total of >1,500 contact points by M18

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to > 10 events by demo leaders • Attendance of >100 persons per events
Step 3: Exploitation of Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing results with relevant groups and communities • Publications of first results and non-confidential information in scientific and technical medias • Attendance and Participation to external events • Maintaining communication • Workshops and Trainings Organisation • Living Labs Organisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased number of followers on social media platforms • Draft of policy guidelines and recommendations • Organisation of workshops, Living Labs, trainings, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >16 Scientific and Technical Publications by M36 • Participation in > 16 scientific conferences by M36 • Organisation of >10 workshops; >6 webinars and >8 online tutorials by M36
Step 4: Sustainability of the Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintaining communication and dissemination efforts to ensure the project's viability (social media campaigns, publications, events, etc.) • Ensure the proper dissemination and exploitation of project's results • Preparing for the next step: survival of the website three years after the end of funding; minimum activity on social medias; exploitation of results by any interested entity thanks to dissemination efforts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance of the website for three years after the end of the funding period • Maintenance of a community through social medias • Participation to conferences and exhibitions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have a total of > 5,000 followers on all social media platforms; and >2,000 total contact points for newsletters • Have distributed a total of >10 newsletter by M36 • Participation in >19 scientific conferences and industrial exhibitions by M36 • >5 contributions to organisations and >5 policy recommendations by M36

To identify these KPIs, it is assumed that the first half of the project will be focused on community growth and outreach, while dissemination and exploitation activities will be implemented from M18 onwards.

Figure 3: Timeline and KPIs

3. THETIDA Audience

The THETIDA project targets a wide range of relevant stakeholders: local and regional administrators, experts and professional groups involved and/or interested in both cultural heritage management and climate change-related issues, as well as cultural and creative industries, SMEs, NGOs, citizens and community groups. Stakeholders have been defined in *D.3.1 THETIDA Living Labs – How to Guide* as “local actors and/or community groups with an interest in, or a relation to the heritage sites in the THETIDA pilot case studies. The stakeholders might have different roles, tasks and responsibilities within the pilot sites”. On another hand, end-users have been defined within the aforementioned document as “groups of people who have a direct interaction or experience with service, tools and products”. It should be mentioned that all end-users can be considered stakeholders, but not all stakeholders are end-users. [3]

Based on these definitions, three target audiences have been identified for the purpose of THETIDA C&D plan, depending on their interest rate and likeliness to be involved with the project results. Therefore, the first audience group will gather end-users and stakeholder with high-level roles, tasks, and responsibilities in relation to the project and its outcomes, and thus a high-interest rate. The second target audience includes end-users and stakeholders with a medium-interest rate in the project as they are likely to be interested in the technologies and methodologies developed but are not directly connected to cultural heritage preservation. Finally, the third target audience aims at gathering stakeholders that are not likely to be end-users, they have an interest in the project, but low-level tasks and responsibilities. The list of stakeholders and end-users identified here is not exhaustive and is likely to change depending on the project developments and results.

Target groups are identified according to their level of interest in THETIDA and their potential connections to the project. Accordingly, target group n°1 is the group with the most direct interest in the project’s objectives, methodology, as well as results whilst target group n°3 is the group with the least direct interest or connections:

- The first target audience includes primary end-users of the solutions developed within the project, as well as its results and outcomes, and stakeholders involved within pilot sites. These entities are considered as primary targets as they will be able to benefit directly from THETIDA’s results.

Key messages: *(i)* Sharing concrete non-confidential results, methods, and products developed within the framework of THETIDA, such as the data coming from the deployed sensors, prediction models, vulnerability map, etc. *(ii)* Disseminating recommendations and policies related to cultural heritage preservation in light of THETIDA data collection and outcomes. *(iii)* Demonstrating Copernicus data set combined with necessary in-situ sensors (smart buoys, AUVs, personal devices, ground sensors) to model and analyse Europe’s underwater and coastal cultural heritage sites and contribute to safeguarding and protecting them.

- Marine monitoring systems, remote sensing, and in-situ sensors developed within the framework of THETIDA are likely to be of interest for entities operating in domains unrelated to cultural heritage preservation. Even though these entities interest in THETIDA's results is strong, their core activities are not directly linked to the project.

Key messages: *(i)* Sharing concrete non-confidential results, methods, and products developed within the framework of THETIDA that can be adapted to uses outside of cultural heritage preservation, such as climate change monitoring technologies and methods, natural hazards prediction tools, etc. *(ii)* Promoting a state-of-the-art and holistic system in risk prevention and management. *(iii)* Demonstrating innovative remote sensing of environmental and pollution stressors through satellite, aerial and ground monitoring, in more general terms than for target audience n°1 which is going to be more closely related to underwater and coastal cultural heritage.
- The THETIDA project also aims at creating an innovative preventive conservation strategy of underwater and coastal heritage by enticing concerned citizens to take part in data collection and monitoring. Therefore, the project also targets the general public, and especially divers and history enthusiasts, climate-oriented citizens, etc. that are not likely to be end-users as for the description provided.

Key messages: *(i)* Raising public awareness on issues involved in preserving Europe's underwater and coastal cultural heritage. *(ii)* Promoting THETIDA cultural heritage pilot sites and the various challenges they are facing to strengthen local communities. *(iii)* Actively engage diverse community groups in participatory and inclusive data acquisition, co-creation and co-design processes through citizen science and participatory Living Lab methodologies.

Table 3: Target Audiences

Target audience n°1	Target audience n°2	Target audience n°3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cultural heritage related SMEs and industries; Policy makers at European, national and local level involved in Maritime Spatial planning and cultural heritage conservation. This includes national authorities and national administrative bodies (e.g., Ministry of Culture), regional authorities and regional governmental bodies (e.g., provinces, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental monitoring agencies; Fishery authorities; Search and rescue agencies; Financing institutions; Entities involved in remote-sensing and in-situ sensors; Climate risk monitoring experts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tourism operators and representatives of tourism industry; General public (including tourists, residents, etc.) Diving centers and divers.

<p>regional water boards), local administrators (e.g, municipalities, local park authorities).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia and research community (including professional experts groups of scientists, heritage experts, etc. anre research institutes and experts); • Coastal and underwater archaeologists; • Site managers; • Technical chambers; • Product developers and users. 		
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NB. The different levels of linkage to the project among the different audiences does not mean that their interest in the project should be questioned or overlooked. These three groups will be equally targeted by C&D activities during the different steps of the C&D plan and of the project. This variety of groups highlights the relevance of the projects results for a multitude of actors and the need for the C&D material to be as customised as possible to effectively address all the identified groups.

4. Tools and Channels

Tools and channels are divided accordingly to their goals, even though they are complementary for the success of the C&D Plan, and for the success of the project at large.

4.1. Communication Strategy

The THETIDA project is targeting a wide audience and must be adapted to each of the targeted audiences aforementioned. Consequently, several tools and channels have been identified and will be used synergistically to ensure effective communication strategy.

When communicating about the project, partners should use the visual identity developed for THETIDA (logos, colour palette and fonts) to allow the different targeted audiences to recognize THETIDA and identify the project. Visual identity further allows targeted audiences to develop connection and familiarity with the project, which helps maintaining their attention and interest all along the project's lifetime.

The communication strategy developed within this deliverable therefore relies on three pillars: the project visual identity and its implementation through online and offline tools. Digital communication campaigns are central to an efficient C&D strategy nowadays as they allow C&D managers to reach out to persons and communities that would not necessarily be reachable through offline medias. Furthermore, as most individuals are looking for information online, an attractive website providing an easy and eye-pleasing access to information helps guaranteeing that online visitors will keep their attention on the project and will be enticed to know more about it and engage with the project. The online presence established with the website must be complemented with a steady presence on social medias to engage and interact with the communities targeted by the project, and to reach out to potentially interested individuals. Social medias allow for real-time and continuous engagement of targeted audiences interested in following the developments of THETIDA and facilitate interactions with stakeholders, and with consortium partners through comments, likes, sharing and reposting of publications. Online tools also complement offline tools by providing more detailed information than promotional material for instance. It should be noted that there is an interconnected relation between online and offline tools as the former helps promoting the later and reciprocally the later redirects audiences to the former.

4.1.1. Visual Identity

Visual identity plays an essential role in branding. Thus, before the conceptualisation of elements constituting the visual identity, project partners met to identify major distinctive elements of the project. For THETIDA communications to be uniform and for the project to stand-out from others, a visual identity has been developed, and is to be used by all consortium partners for both internal and external communications. This branding allows the project to maintain its own identity for the duration of the funding period and after, to be easily recognisable, and to establish consistency and trust with the public. Ergo, it is

recognised that a visual identity should be consistent with the following criteria to be successful:

- Simple and straightforward.
- Representative of the project and its objectives.
- Coherent with the project sector (*e.g.*, academic, professional, cultural, etc.).
- Consistent throughout the different communication tools and channels.
- Unique, to differentiate the project from others.

a. THETIDA Logos

The logo has been created keeping in mind one of the oldest underwater and coastal heritage known to humans: fossils. The main component of the logo therefore combines both seashells – to engage with the underwater and coastal aspect of the project – and history – to engage with the academic and cultural aspect of THETIDA. The spiral shape reminds of the passing of time and evolution of all things and is thus also connected to the notion of preservation and monitoring of elements that can impact underwater and coastal heritage.

Square Logos (blue and white versions):

Long logo:

b. THETIDA Colour Palette and Fonts

The fonts and colours selected are engaging and modern to attract the general public and can also be used in professional and technical communications as they are adequately sober. The main colours (first line) have been selected to reflect the different colours of the sea

depending on the conditions (weather, depth, etc.), and especially the varying colours in THETIDA pilot sites (mainly the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea). Secondary colours (second line) will be used to highlight information and/or elements in a variety of C&D internal and external documents.

Figure 4: THETIDA Colours and Fonts

4.1.2. Online Tools

a. Website

The project website is the main communication tool of THETIDA as it is the core source of information about the project, its objectives, activities, and results. It also contains a direct access to all social media platforms. The [website](#) contains seven main pages that have been identified to provide precise and easily accessible information to online visitors:

- **Home Page:** welcomes online visitors by providing an overview of the project. The first picture that visitors engage with is one of a diver exploring a shipwreck, which immediately reveals to visitors the subject of the project. and by inviting them to subscribe to the newsletter. The home page also features placeholders with shortcut to access all the main pages of the website itself. The visitors get an immediate visualisation of the major location of the pilots' sites through a map developed for the project. Little interactive boxes can be clicked to enter the detailed description of the pilot sites. Specific sections include an overview of the most recent news and events,

this part has been conceived as a carousel with the latest five items displayed. In addition, scrolling further down the page a clear section has been devoted to register to the newsletter as well as to access the library material. Finally, a clickable logo of all partners have been included.

- **About:** is divided into three main sections informing visitors about the project, its objectives and the methodology. The purpose of these pages is to provide insightful information on the content and core processes developed for and by the project.
- **Pilot Sites:** redirect visitors towards pages dedicated to each of the seven THETIDA pilot sites (Algarve, Svalbard, Gallinara Island, Lake Ijssel, La Spezia, Castle of Mykonos, Nissia Shipwreck) and provides detailed information and pictures of the sites. The content of the pilots’ sites page is provided by relevant project partners. The pages fulfil a twofold objective to inform about the pilot sites itself, illustrating its history or current challenges faced due to climate change and to update on developments related to the activities of the project.
- **News & Events:** is used to promote relevant internal and external events attended and/or organised by partners and latest outcomes of the project. This page is additionally populated by relevant piece of news related to the topic of the project and relevant for the activities of the consortium. Social media communications will always rely on an article developed within this webpage to increase the flow of visitors.
- **Project Outputs:** contains all the deliverables to be developed within the framework of THETIDA and their diffusion levels. Along the project all deliverable allowed for public distribution will be uploaded in this page.
- **Library:** it is meant as repository for all publications and presentations relished within the framework of THETIDA, as well as newsletters, and a communication toolkit containing downloadable communication materials.

The website is to be regularly updated to fit the project’s advancements and keep the public and community informed about any relevant event or outcomes. Consequently, it can also be used as a repository of every action and development concerning the project. Screenshots of the current pages of the website can be found in [Annex 2: THETIDA Website Pages](#).

Table 4: Website KPIs

Website KPIs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online by M03 • > 1,500 Unique visitors from M12 • > 5,000 Unique visitors from M36

b. Social Media Channels and Campaigns

THETIDA will complement its online presence through several social media channels to target both ends of our audience (from scientists to citizens). This allows for more interaction with a variety of stakeholders gathering around THETIDA and for a more targeted and community-specific sharing of partners' activities, thanks to the posting and reposting of posts, links, events, and other contents that will be designed *ad hoc* for each platform. Social media channels have been created before the physical kick-off of THETIDA (29th and 30th of June 2023) to engage the consortium in following and sharing them. Social media channels have thus been active since M01, and especially Facebook, Instagram, and LinkedIn accounts. Screenshots of THETIDA social media channels can be found in [Annex 3: THETIDA Social Media Channels](#).

The C&D strategy has been tailored according to the platform used: the content will remain mostly unchanged on the different channels, but the language, formulation and graphic rendering will be adapted to the selected social channel.

- **X (former Twitter):** The account **@Thetida_project** will be used to interact with research and innovation communities and to spread out new publications through concise texts, as well as relevant links and news and events updates. Its shortened content ensures effective and straightforward communication.
- **LinkedIn:** The **@Thetida** account will be used to interact with research and innovation professional communities and to share specific information in a more developed way, especially by taking advantage of the specific groups and communities present on this platform. It targets professionals from different disciplines, in line with THETIDA's holistic approach.
- **Instagram:** The account **@thetida_project** will be used for wide community engagement as its visual interface facilitates a wider outreach and is more entertaining. It allows partners to visually promote the project, and especially the activities carried out in and with pilot sites' partners. Many sites are indeed addressing underwater cultural heritage spots reachable from divers and producing appealing visual material highly relevant for such a kind of media.
- **Facebook:** The **@Thetida** account will be used for wide community engagement as it is the most used social media platform amongst THETIDA partners. This platform favours a visual and written content which allows partners to convey more information than Twitter/X or Instagram and is more accessible than LinkedIn as it is less formal.
- **Podcasts:** will be used for targeted community engagement. This product uploaded on the website, allows to communicate about project results and outcome in a more interactive and detailed form. In depth interview with experts will be scheduled and recorded. It is in line with the project objective to reduce the gap between the scientific/experts community and citizens.

- **TikTok:** although TikTok has been mentioned in the Grant Agreement, the WP6 leader believes that its relevance regarding the THETIDA project is limited as it is a recreational platform with limited professional outcomes, which is not currently in line with the project. TikTok targeted audience is too young for the project purposes. However, if it would be deemed necessary by other project partners a TikTok account could be implemented at a later stage, to engage with mostly diving communities for instance.
- **YouTube:** The **@Thetida** account will be used to post promotional and explanatory videos about the project from M09 to M36. In addition, all the recorded activities from webinars and other hybrid-events will be uploaded on this platform. Thus, the YouTube channel will also be serving as repository of the video content developed.

Eurisy oversees the content-creation and management of the different social media channels for the whole duration of the project. All the THETIDA project partners are called to contribute to the development and timely sharing of material produced for C&D purposes following the Guidelines distributed and attached as Annex 1 of this document.

Table 5: Social Media KPIs

Social Media KPIs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Twitter: reaching by M18 > 500 followers and > 1,000 followers by M36; publishing 4 times a week (excluding <i>ad hoc</i> campaigns) • LinkedIn: reaching by M18 > 1,000 followers and 2,000 by M36; publishing in average twice a week (excluding <i>ad hoc</i> campaigns) • Instagram: reaching by M18 > 500 followers and >1000 by M36; publishing twice a week (excluding <i>ad hoc</i> campaigns) • Facebook: reaching by M18 > 500 followers and >1000 by M36; publishing twice a month (excluding <i>ad hoc</i> campaigns) • YouTube: from M09 onwards, uploading 7 short and self-explanatory videos of the project and interviews. Number of views: > 10,000 • Podcasts: uploading a podcast every two months starting from M12; >200 listeners per podcasts

c. e-Newsletters and e-mail Campaigns

e-Newsletters will provide short descriptions of THETIDA main activities and achievements from M06 onwards. They will allow stakeholders, end-users, and any interested individual to receive regular updates about THETIDA, the project’s results and outcomes, its partners, events in which THETIDA will be mentioned or taking part or organised directly, and any other relevant information. Newsletters will be sent on a quarterly basis to the community and *ad-hoc* and/or special editions will be sent occasionally in order to communicate adequately about specific activities. Online visitors of THETIDA’s website are able to easily subscribe to

the Newsletter from the Homepage, and *ad-hoc* social media posts will promote subscription to the newsletter. The first newsletter is foreseen to be send by the end of M06.

Figure 5: e-Newsletter Website Subscription

Email campaigns to targeted groups is a recognised as highly effective measure of engagement, especially to promote events and outcomes within the specific community and will therefore be used sporadically by C&D WP leader to ensure effective communication of key elements related to the project.

Professional marketing platforms (*i.e.* Mailchimp) will be used to automate the distribution among contact points.

Table 6: e-Newsletter and e-mail Campaigns KPIs

e-Newsletters and e-mail Campaigns KPIs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total mailing list contact points: > 2,000. • Publishing a Newsletter quarterly: 10 e-Newsletter released.

d. General Media Spreading

Results and non-confidential information about the project will also be promoted through online publishing platforms and magazines, newspaper both online and offline, as well as other media (*e.g.* TV or Radio), to raise awareness especially within target group 3.

Non-confidential information about the project will also be disclosed in partners’ national languages to local and regional newspapers, as well as media and press, to ensure its diffusion to local and regional public and raise awareness within local communities about pilot sites and relative use cases, as well as about the project itself.

THETIDA will also connect and execute periodic broad promotion activities in open communities, blog, non-profit organisations and channels such as: Gitter Communities, Nature.com, DownToEarth.

A document listing major national and international sectoral media contact has been developed by Eurisy, uploaded to the project shared repository and distributed for information to project partners.

Table 7: General Spreading KPIs

General Spreading KPIs
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• >15 Press releases• >25 Unique contributions/publications to blogs in > 10 different blogs

4.1.3. Offline Tools and Channels

a. Provision of Communication/ Promotional Material

EURISY will provide partners with necessary promotional material on digital format (e-documents) to communicate about the project when attending events. Major documents will be available online either on the website or on the SharePoint created for the project. All the partners are invited to print the material strictly if needed. Promotional materials include, but is not limited to flyers, brochures, banners, roll-ups, posters and any other laid out paper-based resource. Promotional materials that have already been created can be found in [Annex 4: Promotional Material](#).

- **Flyers:** will be presented as A5 documents and will highlight key non-confidential information and descriptions about THETIDA objective, partners, methodology and results. Their content will evolve considering project's developments. One flyer has been produced in M03 by Eurisy and is currently available both on the SharePoint created for internal sharing of information and on the website. It has been translated into two national languages (French and Italian) and will be translated in all project languages and other languages if needs to be.
- **Brochures:** will be presented as foldable documents to ease their distribution and will highlight key non-confidential information and descriptions about THETIDA and its results. Their content will also evolve with project's developments and results. A first version has been produced in M03 by Eurisy and is available to partners on both the SharePoint and THETIDA website.

Both brochures and flyers have been realised with a professional, easy to read and with a visually appealing design to grab the attention of the reader. The headline as well as the text are concise, catchy, to stimulate the readers' curiosity to know more about the project. Given these characteristics, flyers and brochures can be distributed to every kind of events, especially industry fairs, workshops, whether internal or external. They will be translated into the local language of the country where the event takes place to maximise their informational/educational impact on local entities (citizens, industries, administrations, etc.). Translated content will be transmitted in a

timely manner by consortium partners to EURISY, which will oversee the editing of the material and its distribution.

- **Roll-ups:** will serve as a visual support to promote THETIDA and highlight key project information. The longer format of roll-ups will help capturing the public’s attention and immediately connect with project identity. Given its characteristics, it is a preferred tool for institutional and project branded events as well as for booth and stands dedicated to the project. Since this product is *per se* strongly linked with the project, it will therefore be provided in English only. A first version has been produced by an external company and is attached to Annex 4. It has been distributed among THETIDA partners and is available on the website.
- **Posters:** will primarily serve as a visual aid during scientific events to promote THETIDA methodology and highlight key project information. As they will often change in content depending on the outcome presented, EURISY will provide a general poster in English only. Posters can be presented in a preponderant format or printed and distributed as flyers. A first version has been produced by an external company and is attached to Annex 4. It has been distributed among THETIDA partners and is available on the website.

THETIDA will also explore alternatives (*e.g.*, labelled gadgets and merchandise) as it has proved to be successful promotional instruments, especially with the public.

Table 8: Promotional Material KPIs

Promotional material KPIs
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• > 2,500 printed materials distributed (brochures, flyers, etc.)• > 4 roll-up banners

b. Organisation and Attendance to Events

THETIDA partners will organise events to promote the project and its results and take part in external events to achieve the same goals:

- Internal events are to be defined as local, regional, or international events organised by consortium partners. They include, but are not limited to, trainings, webinars, workshops, living labs, and other engagement activities linked to THETIDA. More specifically, Living Labs are interaction spaces (virtual and real) in which diverse actors collaborate to co-create new solutions to complex challenges, focused on societal/economic problems. These events have been thought to particularly engage with local communities in pilot sites. The Living Labs are meant to raise awareness on the environmental challenges posed by climate change and to provide interactive platforms to ask questions, get information and engage with project partners. They also support C&D activities as they provide visibility, as well as content to be shared

to communities. Deliverable 3.1. provides specific guidelines on how to organise these specific events to partners.

- External events are local, regional, and international events to which partners are participating in as exhibitors, speakers, etc. to promote THETIDA. Partners are called to report internally on these events to facilitate C&D activities and support content creation. External events allow partners to engage with a variety of local, regional and international actors, and to connect with them. Particularly targeted are sectoral events both in the field of technologies applied to cultural heritage, maritime and coastal spatial planning, as well as satellite applications and solutions development, etc. For instance, partners attended the Thessaloniki International Fair (September 2023) and the EUDI SHOW (October 2023).

Events will be targeted and attended according to their targeted public to maintain coherence with the project’s targeted audiences. An excel sheet has been made available to partners on THETIDA SharePoint for them to fill out with foreseeable events that they will organise or take part in. They also have been asked to fill out this document in the Communication Guidelines. The following table is a reproduction of the aforementioned Excel Sheet and will evolve in accordance with events identified by partners.

Table 9: Potential Events

Partner	Event	Event Organiser	Date	Location	Attended
ICCS	Thessaloniki International Fair	HELEXPO	9-17/09/2023	Thessaloniki, Greece	Yes
EURISY	Space-Based Technologies for the Preservation of World Heritage Sites	UNESCO	12/09/2023	Riyadh, Saudi Arabia	No
EURISY	VIPERC - Visual Pattern Extraction and Recognition for Cultural Heritage Understanding 2023	Technical Committee on Automation in Logistics of the IEEE Robotics and Automation Society	25-26/09/2023	Zadar, Croatia	No
EdgeLab, IANTD, UNIPD, MDCA	EUDI Show	SEI srl	13-15/10/2023	Bologna, Italy	Yes
EURISY	5 th International Conference on Heritage and Culture (ICHC)	GARI International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research	21/10/2023	Roma, Italy	N/A

EURISY	Global Ocean Observing System: National Focal Point Forum (Virtual Meeting)	UNESCO	25/10/2023	Online	N/A
CMMI	“Sustainability of the water and energy supply and waste management in Cyprus in the context of a peaceful, fair and workable settlement of the Cyprus Problem and the wider issue of climate change”	Cyprus Peace and Dialogue Center, Glafkos Clerides Institute, Next Century Foundation	26-27/10/2023	Nicosia, Cyprus	N/A
EURISY	Workshop on Cultural Rights and the Protection of Cultural Heritage	United Nations Human Rights – Office of the High Commissioner	01/12/2023	Geneva and online	N/A

Table 10: Events KPIs

Events KPIs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >20 events organised by demo leaders. • > 100 persons per event.

4.2. Dissemination of Scientific and Technical Results

The project’s dissemination measures follow a multi-actor, multi-step, and multi-channel approach. The tools and channels used for the Dissemination of THETIDA results will include:

- **Scientific publications:** Results and outcomes from THETIDA will be published in peer-review open-access journals and presented at scientific conferences. This will allow the scientific community to access these results and to engage with them. To facilitate internal communications, an Excel Sheet listing scientific publications has been uploaded on THETIDA SharePoint and is to be regularly uploaded by partners. The following conferences and journals have been identified within the Grant Agreement:

Table 11: Identified Scientific Publications

Scientific Conferences	Peer-Review Open-access Journals
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Congress for Underwater Archaeology (IKUWA), • IGARSS 2024 symposium, International Astronautical Congress, • AI and Big Data Expo, • European Space Conference, • Europlanet Science Congress, • ESA Living Planet Symposium. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Journal of Nautical Archaeology, • Journal of Marine Sciences and Engineering, • Journal of Eastern Mediterranean Archaeology and Heritage Studies, • International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction, Environmental Research: Climate (ERCL); • Journal of Cultural Heritage (JCH); • Sustainability Science. IEEE Access, • International Journal of Remote Sensing, • Remote Sensing, • Ocean Modelling, • Geoarchaeology, • Archaeological and Anthropological Science; • SpaceNews, • Air & Space Europe, • CEAS Space Journal, • Space Science Reviews, • International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation.

- **Technical publications:** THETIDA will publish and contribute to technical blog posts, articles, position/white papers, catalogues, books or any other reference from technology providers (bottom-up), as well as references related to the application scenarios domains under consideration (top-down). To facilitate internal communications, an Excel Sheet listing technical publications has been uploaded on the THETIDA SharePoint and is to be regularly uploaded by partners.
- **Source code repository:** Encouraging a transparent and open-source culture, THETIDA will make accessible its software repositories through well-known distributed source code platforms (*i.e.*, GitHub and Bitbucket).
- **Q&A Platform:** Conversations about the project repository will be stored in reference sites. The selected Q&A platform is Stack Overflow, the largest and most trusted online community for developers to learn and share knowledge.
- **Workshops and Trainings:** Consortium partners will organise workshops and trainings to associations, authorities, potential investors, funding organisations, ICT SMEs, and Academia regarding the Project results and outcomes.
- **Joint activities with relevant initiatives:** To amplify and maximise the impact and outreach of the project results and to spread them into related international workstreams, joint dissemination activities will be contacted. THETIDA already has

gathered letters of support from 7 different bodies: Associação Geonauta, AMAL, Soprintendenza Liguria, the Ministry of Transport, Communications and Works in Cyprus, CCDR Algalve, the Svalbard Museum, and the Algarve Tourism Board. Moreover, the THETIDA SharePoint comprises a document registering similar projects, funded under the same call and part of the THETIDA community. These projects will also contribute to spreading efforts.

- **Standards and policy contribution:** To achieve high-scale and long-lasting impact, THETIDA aims at influencing standards and policy-making, thus obtaining the seal of approval for the newly implemented components and consequently pushing them into production environments, presenting project’s results for defining future R&I directions based on the project’s acquired knowledge. Consequently, THETIDA partners will draft standards and policy recommendations based on the results of the project and will disseminate these proposals among international organisations, policy makers, and financing institutions, with the help of their members and of policy briefs.

Table 12: Dissemination KPIs

KPIs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >8 Publications in peer-reviewed journals. • >16 Presentations in scientific conferences. • > 25 Technical presentations. • > 3 Participations in industrial exhibitions with booths. • > 13 Available deliverables. • Source Code published within 2 different repositories. • Contribution/Participation to > 25 scientific conversations. • Organisation of >10 technical workshops within 7 different countries and >6 Webinars. • Creation of >8 online training tutorials. • Participation in >9 fairs/symposiums with 3 Banners in each event and >300 brochures to be distributed. • >5 Standards contributions to different organisations and >5 policy recommendations.

4.2.1. Open Science Practices applied in the Project

In accordance with the principle 'as open as possible' wished for the Open Science Policy under Horizon Europe and in line with the reference Grant agreement, THETIDA’s partners will implement appropriate open science practices as an integral part of its methodology.

To enable rapid publication times and publication outputs that support research integrity, reproducibility, transparency and enable open science practices THETIDA consortium partners will use the Open Research Europe scholarly providing open-access to research

outputs and participation in open peer-review. Project participants throughout the project lifetime may need to submit articles to journals (or proceedings) that only offer a lower level of open-access, requiring either parallel publication or an embargo period. The need for this will be evaluated on a *case-by-case* basis and will balance benefits against the less convenient or delayed access to the result. In any case, at least the final author’s version of every accepted paper will be made publicly available, in accordance with the rules posed by many journals. In this respect, the project will use widely self-archiving (or green open access) services for research communities like ResearchGate or Academia, that will allow balance between traditional publications and open-access.

4.2.2. Tools and Channels Summary

In order to provide a complete overview of the various C&D tools identified in this section, the following table has been created to encapsulate the tools, the audiences they target, and their summarised purposes.

Table 13: Tools and Channels Summary

Communication Tools	Target			Purpose
	Target Audience n°1	Target Audience n°2	Target Audience n°3	The purpose is to:
Visual Identity	•	•	•	Enhance project identity and branding.
Website	•	•	•	Provide information to online visitors about the project, its objectives, events and news, and enabling them to subscribe to the Newsletter.
Social Media	•	•	•	Allow real-time and continuous engagement with targeted audiences, as well as interactions with audiences and consortium partners.
e-Newsletters and e-Mail Campaigns	•	•	•	Engage with targeted audiences, announce events and update stakeholders about news related to the project in real-time.
General Media Spreading	•	•	•	Update local/regional/ national audiences about major developments regarding THETIDA.
Promotional Material	•	•	•	Facilitate project’s promotion and information sharing during events (both internal and external).
Organisation and Attendance of/to Events	•	•	•	Share and promote the project and its results with target audiences.

Scientific Publications	• •	Share THETIDA scientific developments and results within scientific communities to ensure adequate dissemination of aforementioned results.
Technical Publications	• •	Share THETIDA technical developments and results within technical communities to ensure adequate dissemination of aforementioned results.
Source Code Repository	• •	Render accessible THETIDA software repositories to encourage a transparent and open-source culture.
Q&A Platform	• •	Ensure access to conversations about the project repository in reference sites.
Workshops and Trainings	• •	Train interested entities on the outcomes and results of the project.
Joint Dissemination Activities	• • •	Amplify and maximise the impact and outreach of the project's results.
Standards and Policy Contributions	•	Achieve high-scale and long-lasting impact of THETIDA results.

5. Internal Communication

The internal communication plan aims to guarantee fluid interactions among partners and avoid misunderstandings, setbacks and any other potential issue hampering the good development of project results. Therefore, internal communication will rely on effective and time-saving exchanges between partners, through user-friendly platforms, to share needs and deadlines for collective actions.

The preferred tool for internal communications will be emails as they ensure targeted and effective communication. Internal communication will also rely on calls, one-on-one and multilateral, via Microsoft Teams or, alternatively and upon discretion, on Skype, Zoom, and/or Google Meet. These calls will take place monthly, as well as at *ad hoc* times, if necessary, to ensure regular updates from the partners on project advancements. Active WPs have been advised by the Project Coordinator (PC) to meet online monthly to update each other on the evolution of their tasks, ask for details to WP partners, and exchange on the desired outcomes of their tasks. These WP monthly meetings are complemented by a monthly meeting of WP leaders (Executive Board meeting) to ensure coordination of WP actions.

Regarding e-mails, partners must ensure that they do not abuse this communication tool, and that they keep their messages concise and clear. Excessive uses would generate confusion amongst partners. To ease email communications, the ICCS (THETIDA PC), created communication lists for each WP and relevant partners in the early beginnings of THETIDA to ensure efficient and seamless communication among the Consortium. The PC should try and safeguard that communication among partners is efficient: meaning that partners answer in a reasonable delay when solicited and uphold respectful communications.

To ease the distribution of relevant documents, the said documents will be uploaded on SharePoint (Microsoft 365) by WP members and made available to all partners. The SharePoint has been created in the early beginnings of the project to ensure efficient teamwork within WP members and among the different WPs. SharePoint allows each member to upload and download documents, facilitating sharing and collaboration.

To help with internal communication, a toolbox has been created and is accessible to all partners on SharePoint, additionally Communication Guidelines (see Annex I) have been drafted and distributed to partners by M05. Communication Guidelines have been produced to ensure correct identification of C&D activities and opportunities from THETIDA partners. Moreover, they detail the toolbox to help partners use its content efficiently. Through a step-by-step approach, the Guidelines also detail the reporting process on C&D activities to be followed by all partners. To facilitate the reporting process, all relevant links can be found within the Guidelines. Following these Communication Guidelines will ensure an active, productive, and transparent communication during the project lifetime.

6. Sustainability Plan

The sustainability of THETIDA project will mostly rely on the effective dissemination of results and outcomes, and of their proper exploitation by targeted groups, especially after the end of the funding cycle. Therefore, project partners expect exploitations activities to be carried out by the scientific/technical/industrial community which will be invited to use and interpret both results and outputs produced by THETIDA partners.

According to the Grant Agreement, the following results and outputs shall be obtained through the implementation of the project activities:

- A holistic method to monitor marine and coastal environments to protect cultural heritage from climate change effects and natural hazards.
- Several participatory processes to monitor marine and coastal environments, relying on cooperation between local administrations, citizens, and experts.
- A demonstrated interest from different stakeholders in the use of marine monitoring methods for both cultural heritage preservation and climate change effects' analysis.
- An increased use of marine monitoring methods by local and regional administrations, as well as by SMEs, and other entities.

These set of indicators and tools will be developed by project partners to monitor the effective exploitation of the above results, identified as basic instruments to grant an adequate project's sustainability.

At the end of the project lifetime, some communication tools described above in Chapter 3 of this document will be maintained active as a shared responsibility among all project partners on an opportunity-based approach.

6.1. Exploitation Strategies

According to the Grant Agreement, THETIDA consortium identified the primary exit market for project outcomes and results to be namely the Marine Monitoring Systems Market. This industry is largely driven by innovative data and tools to monitor water ecosystems. Global marine monitoring systems market is still in its early stage of development and the opportunity to measure environmental conditions in real-time or near-real-time holistic way is expected to propel the demand for these systems in the years to come.

9 user groups using marine monitoring systems have been identified:

- Monitoring of environmental quality;
- Offshore oil and gas;
- Industrial water quality measurements;
- Oceanographic research;
- Fisheries;
- Aquaculture;

- Ocean renewable energy;
- Deep sea mining;
- Port security.

This list illustrates that marine environmental monitoring systems are used in an increasing variety of activities. Thus, there is significant room for sales and profit increase if the actors of the sector apply the correct business models to meet the requirements of their users/clients. It should be noted that end-users groups identified within the Grant Agreement are solely related to underwater cultural heritage.

Secondary exit markets reporting a less intense potential interest in the use of the technologies and systems developed within the project has been identified, including cultural heritage protection/preservation, Disaster or emergency management, environmental monitoring system, coastal and spatial development, archaeological research and others to be identified.

Three different exploitation strategies can be preliminary identified:

- 1) Continuous mapping of users markets segments potentially to better target dissemination and exploitation activities and to update the lists of potential exit markets.
- 2) Licensing of the technologies to SMEs outside of the consortium who in turn develop the necessary methods and equipment.
- 3) Specific attention will be given to establishing connections with service robotic manufacturers, multimedia developers, and other high-tech SMEs and stakeholders.

These points are addressed in order to gradually expand the network.

Within the consortium partners, there are already existing exploitation routes used by individual partners for their own purposes. The THETIDA consortium comprises SMEs and research institutes with solid business plans and market development strategies. Thus, the solutions and products developed within the project will complement the portfolio of solutions and products these partners can put onto the market. For this reason, the THETIDA exploitation strategy will be designed to maximise the impact of individual strategies.

6.2. Project's Sustainability Tools

6.2.1. Online Presence

The project partners will maintain an online presence through the THETIDA branded media for a period of at least three years following the end of the funding cycle by the European Union.

The website will be accessible for three years after the end of the funding cycle to maintain an access to project results and material. Eurisy will create access coordinates to at least one

member per consortium partner in order to allow everybody to publish and upload content in the WordPress page.

During the same period (at least three years after the end of the funding cycle) the social media created for the project will also be maintained.

Project partners will be invited to report to Eurisy any social media content related to THETIDA and uploaded on their own channels, Eurisy in a centralised fashion will gather content and periodically update THETIDA's own social media platforms. Relevant content includes but is not limited to major advancements based on the project results, significant events attended by partners, updates about pilot sites, etc.

6.2.2. Sustainability Communication Guidelines

To ensure that Consortium partners, as well as relevant stakeholders and collaborators identified after the first results of the project, maintain coherence in communications activities related to THETIDA, Sustainability Communication Guidelines will be drafted by Eurisy and distributed among relevant parties in the three months before the end of the funding period by the European Union.

The content of these guidelines will be decided at a later stage, depending on the results of the project and of the success of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities and adapted accordingly. They will provide a framework for THETIDA communications once the funding period ends.

6.2.3. Participatory Processes and Citizen's Involvement

After the end of THETIDA funding period by the European Commission, the participatory initiatives and methodologies developed within the project (living labs, citizens science apps, crowdsourcing activities) are expected to support the overall sustainability of the project thanks to the impact on the larger development of innovative solutions to protect cultural heritage.

Sensitised and trained stakeholders and citizens at large will be able to share the outcomes and results of the project by transferring the gained knowledge (*e.g.* when attending Living Labs, by reading publications and articles about the project, etc.). The citizen engagement dynamic ignited with local participatory processes during the project's funding period is expected to continue thanks to the awareness and the territorial cohesion the project generated within the communities. Ideally by the end of the project, interested stakeholders and local communities alike should feel the ownership of the solutions developed for the benefit of the community itself.

Furthermore, citizen engagement tools developed within THETIDA will also be disseminated to other fields and projects considering the holistic approach that they encompass.

6.2.4. Scientific, Technical and Industrial Engagement with Project's Results

As stated in the Grant Agreement, consortium partners must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules, or legitimate interests. As mentioned above access to THETIDA scientific and technical results will be ensured through open science practices (*i.e.*, open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to results).

Concretely, open access will be granted by the publication of non-confidential results in technical and scientific journals and by the presentation of these results during technical and scientific conferences. This will ensure that the results are shared among scientific and technical communities and submitted to peer-review processes. In addition, THETIDA software(s) repositories will be made available through source code platforms (*e.g.*, GitHub and Bitbucket and conversations about the project repository will be stored within the Stack Overflow Q&A platform, the largest and most trusted online community for developers to learn and share knowledge.

Whilst complying to the open access principle promoted by Horizon Europe, partners will also be allowed to protect THETIDA results and intellectual property rights through licencing. Thus, foreground knowledge (*i.e.* the knowledge developed within the project and its applications) generated by the development of project results will stay within the responsibility of the relevant partner. Besides, any owner of any result will be free to use such results and place it in the market. The potential licencing of any project's results will be an unequivocal indicator allowing for tracing the uses made of results and products. Complementary information regarding intellectual property rights will be disclosed in Deliverable 7.3 'Early project management handbook, and reports on innovation, data and IPR management'.

7. Monitoring Communication and Dissemination Plan's success (KPIs)

To guarantee the effectiveness of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and Activities, key performance indicators (KPIs) have been identified within the present document. These indicators will allow WP6 partners to self-evaluate the effectiveness of the plan and adjust strategies, if necessary, to ensure an optimal support of the THETIDA project.

The data allowing consortium partners to track the evolution of the C&D plan and to report on the results of the KPIs will be collected through various means.

The website impact will be measured through analytical tools such as Google Analytics, complemented in specific cases by the open-source software hosting the THETIDA website.

Social media engagement to channels and posts will be measured through the analytics generated by the platform themselves, such as the number of followers, views, likes, shared content, indicated in the Meta Business Suite (Facebook and Instagram).

For other types of KPIs, a reporting system based on excel documents to be updated periodically by the project partners has been developed. These documents are meant to track publications, contributions, organisations and/or participations to events, etc. More details related to this reporting system are described within the Communication Guidelines (Annex I).

A table summarizing all KPIs necessary to analyse the achievement of C&D objectives has been created and will be updated monthly from M05 to M36 and used to discuss potential adaptation strategies and corrective actions, if necessary.

Depending on the advancements of the THETIDA project, KPIs results will be reported either in D.6.2 Midterm dissemination and exploitation plan and activities or D.6.3 Final dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and activities. Additional KPIs will be added by partners and all along the duration of the project, according to project developments.

The table hereafter presents a summary of KPIs for the THETIDA project:

Table 14: KPIs Summary

KPIs SUMMARY			
KPIs to be reported on by M18 (D.6.2)	Social Media and Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total amount of followers: >2,000 • Publication of at least 2 posts per month on LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook • Publication of at least 4 posts per month on Twitter • Uploading of 4 videos on YouTube • Uploading of 2 to 3 Podcasts • > 1,500 Unique visitors from M12 	KPIs to be reported on by M36 (D.6.3)
	General Spreading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter and mailing list contact points: > 1,000 • 3 to 4 e-Newsletter distributed (quarterly issues) • > 7 Press releases • > 12 Contributions to blogs 	
	Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • > 10 events organised by demo leaders • > 100 persons per event • > 1, 200 printed materials distributed • > 2 roll-up banners 	
	Social Media and Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total amount of social media followers: 5,000 • Publication of at least 2 posts per month on LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook • Publication of at least 4 posts per month on Twitter • 7 videos uploaded on YouTube with 10,000 views • 10 uploaded Podcasts • >5,500 Unique visitors on THETIDA’s website by M36 	
	General Spreading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter and mailing list contact points: >2,000 • 9 Newsletters distributed • > 15 press releases • > 25 contributions to 10 different blogs 	
	Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • > 20 events organised by demo leaders • > 100 persons per event • > 2,500 printed materials distributed • > 4 roll-up banners 	

Dissemination Efforts	Reporting on KPIs related to dissemination efforts might be difficult at this stage depending on the results and outcomes achieved within the THETIDA framework	Dissemination Efforts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >8 Publications in peer-reviewed journals • >16 Presentations in scientific conferences • > 25 Technical presentations • >3 Participations in industrial exhibitions with booths • > 13 Available deliverables • Source Code published within 2 different repositories • Contribution/Participation to > 25 scientific conversations • Organisation of >10 technical workshops within 7 different countries and >6 Webinars • Creation of >8 online training tutorials. • Participation in >9 fairs/symposiums with 3 banners in each event and >300 brochures to be distributed • >5 Standards contributions to different organisations and >5 policy recommendations
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Four Impact Maximisation Objectives (IMO) must be added to these KPIs to have a better understanding of the project impact:

- KPI IMO1.1: Produce and test a ‘how-to guide LLs methodology’ for (local) participatory citizens’ engagement to understand, monitor and assess the impact of climate change on vulnerable underwater and costal cultural landscapes. Results will be reported in deliverable D3.1.
- KPI IMO1.2: Develop both operative and participatory tools to educate and raise citizens’ awareness on the socio-cultural, economic and environmental values of cultural heritage under risk. These include a mobile application which will have 500 registered users by the end of the project.
- KPI IMO1.3: Develop implementation roadmaps for the preservation, adaptation and risk-preparedness of cultural heritage. Report them in deliverable D3.4.
- KPI IMO1.4.: Deliver recommendations for policy makers and report them in deliverable D3.4.

8. Conclusion

This Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan presented herein is tailored to the specific needs of the THETIDA project and provides a solid framework to help partners disseminate decisively project activities and results. This initial C&D plan will be updated in accordance with project progresses to increase the interest of the different actors involved with and targeted by the project, as well as to maximise the awareness and use of THETIDA results among targeted audiences.

The present deliverable establishes strategies to ensure the successful achievement of three key project objectives:

- i) providing effective tools to ensure awareness;
- ii) increasing the overall visibility;
- iii) ensuring the proper dissemination of results.

The achievement of these objectives will be monitored by KPIs, that will be assessed at different moments and specifically at M18 and M36 of project duration. For the purposes of this plan, the project has been divided into four major phases of activities development: **(i)** raise project awareness, **(ii)** grow and target the community, **(iii)** exploit results, and **(iv)** ensure project's sustainability.

The C&D strategy identifies relevant audiences for the project. Within the framework of THETIDA, the targeted audience is divided in three main groups according to their level of direct interest in the project. The first target audience being the most directly linked to the project and its outcomes, and the third being the audience with the most general interest in the project. These audiences will be targeted through a variety of channels and tools, both online and offline. For instance, social media accounts have been established in the early stages of the project and are run by Eurisy with the support of every partner to gather content. A communication toolbox containing promotional material (flyers, brochures, banner, poster) has been made available to partners to facilitate their C&D activities. Other actions such as e-newsletters and publications in general medias and in specific journals will complement the aforementioned actions, as well as the organisation of and attendance to events by THETIDA partners.

To ensure respectful and efficient communications among partners an internal communication plan has been drafted, and it has been specifically detailed in the Communication Guidelines distributed to all partners. In order to grant access to the project outcomes after the end of the funding period, the present C&D plan contains a sustainability plan to allow exploitation strategies to be as profitable as possible, notably by ensuring open access to results and by securing them with adequate credits. Finally, the C&D plan summarises the different KPIs and actions that will be taken during the project lifetime to assure its convenient dissemination.

References

[1] Grant Agreement – Project 101095253 – THETIDA, European Research Executive Agency (REA)

[2] European Research Executive Agency, 16th of June 2023, *Communication, dissemination & exploitation what is the difference and why they all matter*. Available at: <https://rea.ec.europa.eu/publications/> [Last accessed: 02 October 2023]. ISBN: 978-92-95080-88-1 Catalog number: JW-04-23-571-EN-N. DOI: 10.2848/289075

[3] THETIDA (101095253) Deliverable 3.1. THETIDA Living Labs – How to Guide, Deniz Ikiz Kaya (TU/e)

Annex 1: Communication Guidelines

THETIDA
PRESERVING UNDERWATER
AND COASTAL HERITAGE

GUIDELINES TO IDENTIFY AND REPORT ON COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

The THETIDA project foresees extensive communication and dissemination of the project objectives, activities, methodology and outputs.

IDENTIFICATION OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND OUTREACH OPPORTUNITIES

Communication, dissemination and outreach opportunities include **THETIDA-labelled events** and the **presentation of THETIDA** at workshops, conferences and other events, public speeches, publication of articles in printed and online media or websites, dissemination on TV, YouTube channels, etc.

THETIDA-labelled events

A THETIDA labelled event is any sort of event including workshops, conferences, side events and online webinars i) organised by any project's partner for the execution of any project activity; ii) open to external partners; iii) funded with project budget.

To inform us of the THETIDA events you are planning to organise, a table is available on SharePoint: [THETIDA foreseen events.xlsx](#)

Please, fill in this table as soon as you start planning the event and no later than 6 weeks in advance to the event's implementation.

Once the organization of the event is confirmed, please create a subfolder in the appropriate folder and name it in the following format: **DATE_EVENT_NAME_RESPONSIBLE PARTNER** and drop the material (including banners, visuals, videos or other multi-media contents related to the activity) there.

External events

External events are to be considered any kind of event organised by organisations not part of the THETIDA consortium or organised by them but for purposes not directly related with the implementation of project activities featuring the participation of one partner as contributor.

To identify communication, dissemination and outreach opportunities, a table is available on THETIDA's SharePoint: [Potential external events and other communication opportunities.xlsx](#)

Please, fill in this table as soon as you identify the opportunity and no later than 6 weeks in advance to the deadline to propose our contribution to the identified opportunity.

COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES

Effective communication from all partners is important to promote the project and its impacts and results. To avoid creating confusion on the public's mind, it is important to maintain harmonised communication throughout the different platforms all along the duration of the project.

To achieve these two goals of efficiency and coherence, partners are invited to use the [Communication Toolbox](#) available on THETIDA SharePoint when presenting the project internally or externally.

The communication toolbox includes but is not limited to:

- a. Logos (THETIDA and Partners);
- b. Posters, leaflets, banners, brochures (soon to be translated in relevant languages);
- c. Visual identity including colour palette and fonts;
- d. Templates;
- e. A general presentation of the project.

Partners are invited to use appropriate fonts, colours, and general themes when publishing or presenting anything related to the THETIDA project, either on social media or on any other platform. Templates have been created to ease the harmonisation.

In-Person events

When attending to in-person events, partners should use promotional materials as updated on the communication toolbox (leaflets, posters, etc.). Materials are to be used in accordance with the aims of the event attended by the partner. For instance, when organising a THETIDA-labelled event, partners are invited to use the official [roll-up](#) while the [brochure and flyer](#) could also be used for more informal events.

In the week following any events, partners are invited to share with WP6 leader (EURISY) some content to be used on social media (pictures, videos, a short text describing the event itself and the role played by the partner during that event, etc.).

Social Media

Partners are advised to repost/share THETIDA content on their own platforms to develop project visibility and present its advancements.

For external events or THETIDA-labelled events requiring registration/application, effective social media campaigns can help gathering attendance. Therefore, all partners are invited to share on their social platforms the mentioned events.

REPORTING ON COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

Partners are invited to report on the communication, dissemination and outreach activities for which they are responsible **within the week following the implementation of such activities**. To facilitate the reporting process, a step-by-step procedure has been developed, and is relying on the following folder: [Reporting on Communication, Dissemination and Outreach Activities](#).

If you are not able to access SharePoint, please send the required information via email to anais.guy@eurisy.eu.

Description & Purpose

Dissemination activities related to results achieved within the framework of THETIDA (i.e., publications or presentations of work done within the framework of THETIDA, such as journal publications, technical articles, participation in conferences, etc.) **must be approved beforehand by the THETIDA Consortium**.

The dissemination procedure is to be followed by all partners equally, regarding every dissemination activity (including activities unrelated to results dissemination, such as participation to events, exhibitions, use of leaflets and brochures, etc. for which steps 4 to 6 do not apply) to:

- a. Produce high quality THETIDA publications and presentations;
- b. Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- c. Efficiently monitor, record and promote the dissemination activities of the project;
- d. Secure the brand identity of the project and the EC rules to be followed;

The WP6 leader (EURISY) is responsible for ensuring compliance with the procedures. **All partners are called to contribute efficiently to the dissemination of the project.**

Step by Step Procedure

Before any dissemination activity related to the THETIDA project, the initiator of the activity should:

STEP 1: Notify WP6 Leader (Anaïs Guy: anais.guy@eurisy.eu, Annalisa Donati: annalisa.donati@eurisy.eu) & THETIDA's Coordinator Team (Panos Michalis: p.michalis@iccs.gr, Dimitris Maragkos: dimitris.maragkos@iccs.gr), **at least 30 working days in advance** about the intention to participate on a dissemination activity, sharing the details of the activity (date of event, name of journal, title of activity, audience, etc.), their specific role in it (presenter, organiser, speaker in a session, etc.) a short description (up to 150 words) of the activity and how it is related to THETIDA (see *Table n°1: Relevant information* below);

STEP 2: Register the activity in the [Dissemination Registry](#) specifying all the details regarding the activity, as indicated in each column of the file;

STEP 3: If applicable, **store the relevant material** (abstract, draft paper, poster, article, presentation, press release etc.) in the [Reporting on Communication, Dissemination and Outreach Activities](#) on Teams, under the related sub-folder:

- a. [Articles and Publications](#): Records information about articles, publications and contributions related to THETIDA published in printed and online journals, publications and webpages.
- b. [Communication on Media](#): Records information about communication, dissemination and outreach made through printed and online media.
- c. [External Events](#): Records information about workshops, conferences, and other events to which you contributed by providing information or materials about THETIDA.
- d. [Our Events](#): Records information about workshops, training, and other THETIDA-labelled events.

Once in the sub-folder, please create a folder in the following format **DATE_ACTIVITY NAME_RESPONSIBLE PARTNER** and drop the materials there.

STEP 4: WP6 leader has 2 days to react and send the request to the Consortium for approval, modification or rejection;

STEP 5: Any Consortium member may raise a modification or rejection request along with comments which should be sent to the WP6 leader within 15 days; no response is considered as an approval;

STEP 6: The WP6 leader informs the initiator of the dissemination activity and the Project Coordinator about the decision.

In case of:

- a. **Approval:** The initiator may proceed with the submission or realization of the planned dissemination activity;
- b. **Conflict/objection:** Any Consortium member can object to the proposed dissemination activity, for example in cases of risk of disclosure of restricted or confidential information. The objection has to include a clear reasoning as well as a precise request for necessary modifications that would make the dissemination acceptable.

The issue is discussed among the Coordinator, the WP6 Leader and the involved partners.

Dissemination Activities Report

Within **ten working days after the realisation of the dissemination activity**, the partner should upload a fully filled [Dissemination Report](#) together with the dissemination material presented (*i.e.* final paper, presentation, poster etc.) on the [Dissemination Activity Inventory](#) accessible anytime by any project partner. It is recommended that the lead partner of every dissemination activity provides the WP6 Leader with pictures/videos of the participation at the event. The partners are requested to complete all the fields briefly and clearly, trying to avoid the use of abbreviations.

EU Acknowledgement

Since 2021, all recipients of EU funds have the legal obligation to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received EU funding. This requirement ensures visibility and transparency. For projects funded under Horizon Europe, this requirement is specified under Article 17 of the Grant Agreement. The obligation requires all beneficiaries, managing authorities and implementing partners of EU funding to acknowledge the support from the European Union on all communication materials. An important element with this regard is the European Union emblem and the funding statement which

must be displayed prominently¹ on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels and other communication products:

Horizontal:

**Funded by
the European Union**

Vertical:

**Funded by
the European Union**

For any communication activity, presentation, on-line material, hard copy/printed material, the EU emblem must be displayed, along with the phrase:

“THETIDA project is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

For any infrastructure & equipment, the EU emblem must be displayed, along with the phrase:

“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of the THETIDA project, which is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

For any (scientific) publication/technical paper, the acknowledgement must be displayed as follows:

“This research has been conducted as part of the THETIDA project, which is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Useful Links

Dissemination Folder	SharePoint Access
Dissemination Activities Registry	SharePoint Access
Dissemination Report	SharePoint Access
Dissemination Activity Inventory	SharePoint Access

Table n°1: Relevant information

TITLE OF ACTIVITY	
Description / Short Summary	
Relation to THETIDA	

Annex 2: THETIDA Website Pages

1) Homepage

2) About

3) Consortium

INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS (ICCS), GREECE

ICCS is a non-profit, private legal entity linked to the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA). It is the research host of the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (SECE), promoting Research and Development in all its different research disciplines.
i-sense.iccs.gr

EDGELAB SRL (ELB), ITALY

EdgeLab s.r.l. is a high-tech SME, working on innovative equipment and solution using AUV, underwater robotics, sea technologies and sensors. EdgeLab conceives, designs and realises underwater systems and miniaturised sensor solutions.
www.edgelab.eu

4) Pilot Sites

Pilot sites

<p>Consolidated B24-Liberator (PB4Y-1)</p> <p>The Netherlands</p> <p>Know more</p>			
<p>Equa WWII steel shipwreck</p> <p>Cyprus</p> <p>Know more</p>			

5) News & Events

The screenshot shows the 'News & Events' page of the THETIDA website. The navigation bar includes links for HOME, ABOUT, CONSORTIUM, PILOT SITES, NEWS & EVENTS (highlighted), PROJECT OUTPUTS, and LIBRARY, along with social media icons for Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube. The main heading is 'News'. Below it, there are three news items:

- THETIDA at the Thessaloniki**: Accompanied by an image of a person holding a THETIDA informational poster at an event.
- THETIDA's Press Release**: Accompanied by a news article snippet with a photo of a stone fortification. The text below reads: 'I-SENSE Group of ICCS, coordinator of THETIDA project.'
- THETIDA: the new European project for the protection of Coastal and Underwater Cultural Heritage has just started!**: Accompanied by a group photo of project members.

6) Project Outputs

The screenshot shows the 'Project Outputs' page of the THETIDA website. The navigation bar is identical to the previous page. The main heading is 'Project Outputs'. Below the heading, there is a large banner image showing a coastal scene with a stone wall and wooden chairs. The word 'THETIDA' is overlaid on the image.

Project Outputs

D1.1 THETIDA End User Needs

Sensitive

7) Library

Communication Toolkit

- Project Logos

THETIDA logo long_white_transparent background
THETIDA logo long_blue_transparent background
THETIDA logo long_blue
THETIDA logo long_white
THETIDA logo square
THETIDA logo_square_blue
THETIDA logo_square_blue_transparent background
THETIDA logo_square_white_transparent background

- Project Visual Identity

Annex 3: THETIDA Social Media Channels

1) X (Twitter)

2) LinkedIn

3) Instagram

4) Facebook

5) YouTube

The screenshot shows the YouTube channel page for THETIDA. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "Rechercher" and a microphone icon. Below the search bar is a large video thumbnail showing a diver underwater. The channel name "Thetida" is displayed, along with the handle "@Thetida", 6 subscribers, and "Aucune vidéo". The channel description reads: "THETIDA - Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustain...". The website "thetida.eu" is listed. Navigation tabs include "ACCUEIL", "CHAÎNES", and "À PROPOS". The "Description" section contains the text: "THETIDA - Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution." and "The THETIDA project approaches safeguarding and protecting Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage from the effects of climate change and natural hazards in a holistic manner that includes risk management, protection and preparedness, as complementary strategies to prevent damages to cultural heritage (CH) sites, identify and ward off additional threats and promote policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas." The "Statistiques" section shows "Actif depuis le 9 juin 2023". A "Liens" section includes the "Project website" link "thetida.eu".

Annex 4: Promotional material

1) Flyers

Recto:

THETIDA

The THETIDA project aims at safeguarding and protecting Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage from the effects of climate change and natural hazards

PROJECT GOALS

- Develop **methods for risk management, protection and preparedness**, and strategies to prevent damage to cultural heritage sites;
- Identify and **ward off threats**;
- Deliver **policy tools for climate neutrality** and economic resilience in coastal areas;
- Develop, test and validate an **integrated multiple Heritage Risk Assessment and Protection System** with evidence-based monitoring

PARTNERS

ICGS, Marina Diving Center, Centro Ciência Viva Algarve, Eurisy, TU/e, UAlg, ResilienceGuard, niku, University of Cyprus, Ephorate of Antiquities of Cyclades, Dipartimento di Geoscienze, SignalGeneriX, MOOI Noord-Holland, Università degli Studi di Padova, Cyprus Marine & Maritime Institute, Norwegian Institute for Cultural Heritage Research.

Verso:

PILOT SITES

- NORWAY:** Hlorthamn Coal cableway station, Svalbard, Norway
- NETHERLANDS:** Lake IJssel, The Netherlands
- ITALY:** Gallinara Island, Italy; Equa WWII steel shipwreck, La Spezia, Italy
- GREECE:** Castle of Mykonos Town, Greece
- PORTUGAL:** Consolidated B24-Liberator (PB4Y-1), Algarve, Portugal
- CYPRUS:** Nissia Shipwreck, Cyprus

CONTACTS

- Website: <https://thetida.eu>
- Email: info@thetida.eu
- Twitter: @Thetida_project
- LinkedIn: THETIDA
- Instagram: thetida_project
- YouTube: @Thetida
- Facebook: Thetidaproject

Project Coordinator
Dr. Angelos Amditis, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS)

Grant Agreement: 101095253
 Start Date: 1 May 2023
 End Date: 31 October 2026

Funded by the European Union
 Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Funded under: Culture, creativity and inclusive society.

2) Brochures

THETIDA

The THETIDA project aims at safeguarding and protecting Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage from the effects of climate change and natural hazards

PROJECT GOALS

- Develop **methods for risk management, protection and preparedness**, and strategies to prevent damage to cultural heritage sites;
- Identify and **ward off threats**;
- Deliver **policy tools for climate neutrality** and economic resilience in coastal areas;
- Develop, test and validate an **integrated multiple Heritage Risk Assessment and Protection System** with evidence-based monitoring frameworks, innovative tools and instruments, and through participatory processes.

Funded by the European Union

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Funded under: Culture, creativity and inclusive society.

Project Coordinator
Dr. Angelos Amditis, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS)
Grant Agreement: 101095253
Start Date: 1 May 2023
End Date: 31 October 2026

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 THETIDA
 thetida_project
 @Thetida
 Thetidaproject

PILOT SITES

NORWAY

Hiorthhamn Coal cableway station
Svalbard, Norway

NETHERLANDS

Lake IJssel
The Netherlands

ITALY

Gallinara Island
Italy

ITALY

Equa WWII steel shipwreck
La Spezia, Italy

GREECE

Castle of Mykonos Town
Greece

PORTUGAL

Consolidated B24-Liberator (PB4Y-1)
Algarve, Portugal

CYPRUS

Nissia Shipwreck
Cyprus

PARTNERS

3) Roll-up Banner

THETIDA
PRESERVING UNDERWATER AND COASTAL HERITAGE

THETIDA

Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution.

Project Goals

- Develop methods for risk management, protection and preparedness, and strategies to prevent damage to cultural heritage sites;
- Identify and ward off threats;
- Deliver policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas;
- Develop, test and validate an integrated multiple Heritage Risk Assessment and Protection System with evidence-based monitoring frameworks, innovative tools and instruments, and through participatory processes.

Project Coordinator: Dr. Angelos Amditis, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS)
Start date: 1 May 2023 **End date:** 31 October 2026

Partners

www.thetida.eu @Thetida_project @Thetida Thetida_project Thetidaproject THETIDA

Funded by the European Union

The THETIDA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement 101082251. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

4) Poster

THETIDA

PRESERVING UNDERWATER AND COASTAL HERITAGE

Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution.

Project Goals

- Develop methods for risk management, protection and preparedness, and strategies to prevent damage to cultural heritage sites;
- Identify and ward off threats;
- Deliver policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas;
- Develop, test and validate an integrated multiple Heritage Risk Assessment and Protection System with evidence-based monitoring frameworks, innovative tools and instruments, and through participatory processes.

Project Coordinator: Dr. Angelos Amditis, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS)

Start date: 1 May 2023 **End date:** 31 October 2026

Partners

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Funded by the European Union

The THETIDA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement 101095253. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

